

Key performance indicators relevant to floating renewable energy systems/D5.1

WP5, T5.1

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Executive Summary

This deliverable focuses on key performance indicators (KPIs) that can be utilized to evaluate technological innovations and concepts for offshore wind and renewable energy projects. Migrating from the traditional Levelized Cost Of Energy (LCOE)-focused assessment, we conduct a detailed investigation of environmental and social indicators, briefly presenting the quantification relationship, relevance to the issue, advantages and limitations of each identified indicator.

This deliverable has been developed building on deliverable D1.2, thereby following a similar structure and logic. It complements the framework initiated by D1.2 which covered technical and financial KPIs, by providing a comprehensive review of environmental and social KPIs, and a shortlist of such KPIs to be considered for sustainability impact assessment for the development of Floating Offshore Wind (FOW) renewable energy infrastructure.

A combination of systematic and targeted literature review has been used to ensure comprehensive and reliable analysis. Peer reviewed literature has been complemented with other sources including websites of internationally recognized organizations such as the International Labour Organization (ILO), the US Agency for International Development (USAID), and TAILWIND key internal documents.

Some of these indicators are based on the literature, other are relevant to the project outcomes and will be validated during the project implementation by engaging stakeholder in defining the appropriate ones in relation to specific sites where LCOE has been adopted.

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose and scope

Interrelation with other Deliverable and Tasks

This deliverable complements the framework introduced by D1.2 for evaluating floating offshore wind configurations and technological innovations, through a combination of multi-attribute key performance indicators (KPIs) that account for key sustainability dimensions. Technical and financial KPIs were analyzed in D1.2; this deliverable focuses on environmental and social KPIs. Together, these two deliverables provide a very comprehensive review of available KPIs able to characterize the impact of TAILWIND innovations through this comprehensive yet adaptable framework and will further inform activities in subsequent work packages. In addition, this deliverable has informed will activities of Task 3.1, and will inform T5.2, T5.3 and T5.4.

To this end, this deliverable aims to collect and categorise an extensive list of indicators that can be used not only for comparative purposes, but also as objectives for the design and optimization of modern offshore wind farms.

A key element of the analysis is the classification of the information into different groups and subgroups in order to allocate the collected KPIs.

For environmental KPIs we identified six main categories:.

- Emission and pollution
- Resource use and sustainability
- Ecosystem and biodiversity
- Waste management and end-of-life
- Energy efficiency and investment return
- Climate resilience and global impact

For the socio-economic KPIs we identified four main categories:

- Impacts on local economy including job creation
- Working conditions
- Local workforce upskilling and reskilling
- Impacts on landscape and social acceptance

Table 1 shows an overview of the number of indicators for each category.

Table 1 Brief overview of six Environmental and four Social categories and the number of proposed KPIs for each category

	Environmental KPIs	Socio-economic KPIs
Emissions and Pollution	6	
Resource use and sustainability	4	
Ecosystem and biodiversity	4	
Waste management and end-of-life	3	
Energy efficiency and investment return	4	
Climate resilience and global impact	2	
Impacts on local economy including job		5
Working conditions		5
Local workforce upskilling and reskilling		2
Impacts on landscape and social acceptance		5

Relation to project objectives

This deliverable directly contributes to the objectives and key exploitable results of the TAILWIND project, specifically:

- Objective 3 (O3): Quantify and integrate in the design process the impact of floating offshore wind (FOW) parks on economy, society, and environment.
- Specific Objective 3.2 (SO3.2): Identification of sustainable KPIs and their integration into the life cycle impact assessments of the developed technologies.
- Key Exploitable Result (KER) 12: KPIs and life cycle assessment tool for integrated impact of FOW.

In addition to the contribution of the technical and economic KPIs set out in D1.2, D5.1 contributes to the definition of potential social indicators that will be integrated in the life cycle module developed in T5.2 and T5.3

This deliverable will contribute to T5.4 by identifying specific KPIs to measure the impact of FOW technologies on local economies; validation with stakeholders will be made during the definition of the two case studies in Denmark and Germany.

Deliverable structure

This deliverable is organized into four sections. Following this brief introduction, the methodology for the KPI definition is presented in Section 2. Then, the analysis of specific KPIs for environmental and social aspects of FOW is included in Section 3. Conclusions on how to adapt such KPIs for use in sustainable life cycle assessment are included in Section 4.

2. Methodology for identifying environmental and social KPIs

2.1. Theory of Change

The Theory of Change (ToC) is an approach articulating the logical flow between a key problem and its immediate and root causes, the long-term change it seeks to bring about in response to this key problem, and what needs to happen for this change to come about.

A ToC provides an overarching picture of the project's intended pathway of change, explaining how the intervention is expected to interact with other concurrent interventions and contextual conditions to enable a series of outcomes at various levels of an objectives hierarchy, including intermediate results (IRs), strategic objectives (SOs) and project goal.

The ToC can be presented graphically or as a narrative explanation of how the various elements of the project and associated assumptions fit together, and how and why a desired change is expected to happen.

The proposed ToC model has been developed primarily based on the project description in the grant agreement, with some feedback gathered during the work on T5.1.

This model is based on some specific assumptions about the **long-term impacts** that the project aims to contribute to:

- There is a need to contribute to the European Commission's strategy to meet specific targets sets in the Green Deal;
- There is a need for more for enhancing protection and resilience across all stages of the supply chain for the renewable energy sector;
- Increased knowledge, sharing of best practices and spill-over effects can help the implementation of FOW infrastructures in a more sustainable way;
- The consideration of social aspects in the implementation of FOW parks can reduce conflicts with other sea users and increase social acceptance of this type of renewable energy infrastructure.

Considering the assumption of long-term impacts, **specific outcomes** to be validated in the TAILWIND project can be defined as follow:

- Improvement in the performance of FOW parks and reduction in the costs of this renewable energy;
- Improvements in the use of marine space can come from the efficiency in the implementation of FOW technologies;
- Projects such as TAILWIND can help reducing the environmental impacts of FOW;
- A reduction of the footprint of raw materials used in the FOW can be analyzed;
- Positive impacts on local economies can be achieved in the implementation of FOW parks, on jobs conditions and skills of workers.

In terms of **outputs**, the project will work on some specific Key Exploitable Results:

- Optimize the design of FOW infrastructures;
- Further characterize existing mooring materials;

- Test and validate new anchor installation processes;
- Test and validate new frameworks for FOW implementation (such as analysis of soil behavior);
- Databases of material properties that could decrease the environmental impact, support European supply chain, or cut project costs.

Project partners are all qualified to address the challenges that have been found common to the development of FOW infrastructures in different settings. The implementation of TAILWIND project activities and the involvement of an Expert Advisory Board are **inputs** of the strategy developed by the project partners to achieve the project objectives and contribute to these challenges.

2.2. Approach to KPI Definition

To allow for a comprehensive consideration of key performance indicators (KPIs) for floating offshore wind energy systems, a combination of targeted and systematic literature review approach has been chosen, as this methodology allows for an objective and replicable approach to collecting, classifying and reporting information available to the academic body of knowledge. Through this approach, we rely on databases, such as Scopus, which covers a vast number of peer-reviewed sources, offering reliable sources for synthesizing conclusions. Core to the process is the careful and inclusive selection of keywords as outlined in the next section. Once the relevant sources are collected, manual screening takes place for relevance and completeness based on the broader understanding developed during the review process.

A broad classification of KPIs includes four categories: technical, economic, environmental, and societal indicators. This deliverable covers a review of environmental and societal KPIs, while technical and economic KPIs have been covered in deliverable D1.2. The two deliverables will be combined in a thorough review paper, potentially in collaboration with other projects of the same European call. The identification, selection and use of KPIs is a starting point for screening several technological options that have been developed, and further analysis will be the work focus of subsequent WPs.

Methodology for the identification of Social KPIs and Environmental KPIs

The following documents and information have been used to set the foundations for the research on social KPIs:

- The list of key outcomes and impacts of interest identified in TAILWIND's Grant Agreement
- The criteria developed by DTU on industrial feasibility assessment presented in D1.2

A targeted literature review has been conducted, focusing on peer-reviewed papers on sustainability assessment of renewable technologies, and including some sources related to development projects and operation and maintenance in the marine sector. The search for articles has included the following keywords in different combinations: *sustainability, indicators, KPIs, impact assessment, social impacts, environmental*

impacts, impacts on local economy, renewable energy, as well as maritime industry. Precedence has been given to reviews of reviews and sourced referenced in those. Other sources have also been considered in relation to specific themes, for example ILO methodology has been reviewed relative to working conditions assessment.

A long list of KPIs has been identified building on input from the literature. KPIs have then been shortlisted based on **relevance** (in relation to prevalence in the literature, and mention in the Grant Agreement) and **validity** (appropriateness to represent the outcome or impact of interest). Further shortlisting is recommended at the operational stage to identify the specific KPIs that will be measured for the TAILWIND project, with regards to the two case studies foreseen (Denmark and Germany). This will be done during the T5.2, T5.3, and T5.4 implementation.

3. KPIs relevant to FOW

In this section we will explore the specific KPIs that have been selected through the methodology explained in Chapter 2.

In this project specific attention is given to the sets of KPIs that come from the literature and to the adaptation needed for the specific aim of this project, and then to those project-specific KPIs that have been discussed with project partners. For each set of indicators (environmental and social) tables are included in the Deliverable explaining the specific indicator, the formula to calculate it, the sources to retrieve data for the calculation, and a list of pros and cons to consider it a useful indicator for the aim of the project.

3.1. Environmental KPIs

Environmental KPIs have been grouped into the following six main categories:

- Emission and Pollution
- Resource Use and Sustainability
- Ecosystem and Biodiversity
- Waste Management and End-of-Life
- Energy Efficiency and Investment Return
- Climate Resilience and Global Impact

In the following, a description of the definition and considerations for the use of all individual KPIs is given.

Emissions and Pollution KPIs

The carbon footprint represents the total greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions associated with a renewable energy system throughout its lifecycle, from construction and operation to decommissioning (Li et al., 2023). Measured in tons of CO₂ equivalent (tCO₂e), it provides a holistic view of a system's contribution to climate change. Reducing the carbon footprint is a key driver of renewable energy adoption. This indicator helps stakeholders assess how much a system offsets emissions compared to traditional energy sources and aids in decision-making for meeting sustainability and climate goals, particularly in achieving net-zero emissions targets (Saqib, 2022).

The air quality impact measures the effect of a renewable energy system on local air quality, accounting for emissions of pollutants like nitrogen oxides (NO_x), sulfur oxides (SO_x), and particulate matter during construction and operation (Akça, 2023). Though renewable energy systems typically have minimal operational air emissions, this metric is particularly important for assessing the impact of related activities, such as transportation or site development (Fan et al., 2024). Improving air quality is one of the primary benefits of switching from fossil fuels to renewables, and this indicator helps ensure that any short-term construction impacts are managed effectively.

Noise pollution measures the level of noise generated by renewable energy systems during operation (Senyapar & Bayindir, 2023). This is particularly relevant for wind farms, where turbine noise can affect nearby communities and wildlife. Measured in

decibels (dB), this indicator helps assess whether noise levels remain within acceptable limits, especially in sensitive areas. Noise pollution can affect public acceptance of renewable energy projects and contribute to negative health impacts. By monitoring and mitigating noise levels, developers can improve the social and environmental compatibility of wind and solar energy projects, ensuring broader acceptance and regulatory compliance (Tsouvalas, 2020).

Lifecycle emissions intensity measures the total greenhouse gas emissions produced per unit of energy generated over the system's entire lifecycle, including construction, operation, and decommissioning (Sandwell et al., 2016). Expressed in grams of CO₂ equivalent per kilowatt-hour (gCO₂e/kWh), it provides a comprehensive measure of the environmental efficiency of a renewable energy system. This indicator is key for comparing the sustainability of different energy technologies, ensuring that renewable energy projects not only reduce emissions during operation but also account for emissions generated during manufacturing, transport, and eventual decommissioning.

Supply Chain Carbon Intensity measures the carbon emissions generated throughout the entire supply chain of a renewable energy project, from material extraction to component manufacturing and transportation (Lee et al., 2022). This metric is critical for ensuring that the environmental benefits of renewable energy are not undermined by high upstream emissions. It helps project developers identify carbon-intensive processes in their supply chains and implement strategies to reduce emissions. By considering both direct and indirect emissions, this KPI provides a holistic view of a project's carbon footprint, supporting more sustainable procurement and manufacturing practices in renewable energy systems.

Toxic Emissions Intensity evaluates the quantity of toxic pollutants, such as heavy metals and hazardous chemicals, released throughout the lifecycle of a renewable energy system (Chordia et al., 2021). These emissions often occur during manufacturing, transportation, and decommissioning processes. This metric is important for assessing the indirect environmental and human health impacts of renewable energy technologies. Systems with high toxic emissions intensity may undermine their environmental benefits, despite producing clean energy. By measuring and reducing toxic emissions, developers can improve the environmental sustainability of renewable energy systems, ensuring that harmful pollutants do not offset their climate advantages.

Table 2: Emissions and Pollution KPIs

Indicator	Description	Unit	Formula	Relevance	Pros	Cons
Carbon Footprint	The total greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions produced directly and indirectly by the energy system over its lifecycle.	Tons of CO ₂ equivalent (tCO ₂ e)	Carbon Footprint = Σ (GHG Emissions during all phases)	Essential for assessing the environmental impact of renewable energy systems in the context of global climate goals.	Provides a clear measure of greenhouse gas emissions; Helps assess a project's contribution to climate goals; Widely recognized for environmental reporting	Focuses only on carbon emissions, ignoring other pollutants; May not account for full lifecycle emissions; Difficult to reduce to zero in practice
Air Quality Impact	The effect of the energy system on local air quality, including emissions of pollutants like NO _x , SO _x , and particulate matter.	Concentration (µg/m ³)	Air Quality Impact = Σ (Pollutant Emissions) / Total Air Volume	Important for assessing the broader environmental health impacts of renewable energy systems, especially during construction.	Highlights local environmental health effects; Important for reducing air pollution from construction and operational phases	Focuses mainly on local pollutants rather than broader environmental effects; Often temporary during construction phases

<p>Noise Pollution</p>	<p>The level of noise generated by the renewable energy system during operation, particularly for technologies like wind farms.</p>	<p>Decibels (dB)</p>	<p>Noise Pollution = Sound Level at Source - Attenuation Factor</p>	<p>Relevant for understanding the social and ecological impacts of renewable energy systems, particularly in sensitive areas.</p>	<p>Important for assessing public and wildlife impacts; Critical for wind farm and infrastructure planning</p>	<p>Highly location-dependent; Can be minimized with better design and planning; Ignores non-auditory environmental impacts</p>
<p>Lifecycle Emissions Intensity</p>	<p>The total emissions produced per unit of energy generated over the system's lifecycle.</p>	<p>Grams of CO₂ equivalent per kWh (gCO₂e/kWh)</p>	<p>Emissions Intensity = Total Lifecycle Emissions / Total Energy Produced</p>	<p>Key metric for comparing the sustainability of renewable energy technologies in terms of their greenhouse gas emissions.</p>	<p>Measures total emissions over the lifecycle of the project; Important for comparing long-term sustainability of different technologies</p>	<p>Requires accurate data on emissions throughout the lifecycle; Does not account for non-emissions-based environmental impacts</p>
<p>Supply Chain Carbon Intensity</p>	<p>Measures the carbon emissions associated with the entire supply chain of renewable energy projects, from material extraction to component manufacturing.</p>	<p>Grams of CO₂ equivalent (gCO₂e)</p>	<p>Supply Chain Carbon Intensity = Σ (CO₂ Emissions per Supply Chain Activity)</p>	<p>Important for evaluating the total carbon impact of renewable energy systems, including upstream and downstream activities.</p>	<p>Measures upstream carbon emissions; Important for assessing full carbon footprint beyond operational emissions</p>	<p>Requires detailed supply chain analysis; May overlook non-carbon environmental impacts like water or habitat loss</p>

<p>Toxic Emissions Intensity</p>	<p>Measures the intensity of toxic emissions, such as heavy metals and hazardous waste, generated throughout the lifecycle of the energy system.</p>	<p>Kilograms of toxic emissions per kWh (kg/kWh)</p>	<p>Toxic Emissions Intensity = Σ (Toxic Emissions during Lifecycle) / Total Energy Output</p>	<p>Important for evaluating the indirect environmental impacts of renewable energy systems, particularly during material extraction and disposal.</p>	<p>Quantifies the environmental harm from toxic by-products during lifecycle phases; Important for ensuring safe material use and disposal</p>	<p>Requires detailed emissions data for all lifecycle stages; Can vary greatly across different technologies and manufacturing processes</p>
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Resource Use and Sustainability KPIs

The water footprint measures the total volume of freshwater consumed during the construction, operation, and decommissioning of a renewable energy system (J. Zhang et al., 2019). This indicator is expressed in cubic meters (m³) and is important for assessing water use efficiency, particularly in regions facing water scarcity. Technologies like solar and wind have relatively low water footprints compared to traditional fossil fuel systems, but understanding the full lifecycle water use is critical (Lohrmann et al., 2021). It helps operators and regulators identify areas where water use can be reduced, making the project more sustainable in water-sensitive environments.

Land use impact measures the amount of land required for the installation, operation, and maintenance of renewable energy infrastructure (G. C. Wu et al., 2020). Typically measured in hectares (ha), this indicator helps assess the spatial footprint of energy projects. It's particularly relevant for large-scale installations like solar farms or onshore wind farms that require significant land areas. By quantifying land use, stakeholders can evaluate the trade-offs between energy generation and potential ecological disruption (Lamhamedi & de Vries, 2022). Optimizing land use efficiency is key for minimizing environmental damage, habitat destruction, and competition with other land uses, such as agriculture or conservation.

Embodied Energy in Materials refers to the total energy consumed to extract, process, and transport materials used in constructing renewable energy systems (Zecevic et al., 2020). It is crucial for lifecycle analysis, as renewable systems may require significant energy upfront to produce components like wind turbines, solar panels, or batteries. This metric reveals the hidden energy costs embedded in the project, which could influence its overall sustainability. Understanding embodied energy helps designers and operators optimize material choices, prioritize low-energy alternatives, and reduce the project's total energy footprint. It's especially relevant for reducing the environmental impacts of manufacturing and supply chains.

The Resource Depletion Index (RDI) measures the consumption of non-renewable and critical materials used in the construction and operation of renewable energy systems (Afsari Mamaghani et al., 2023). It highlights how much of these finite resources are being extracted relative to their global reserves. RDI is crucial for understanding the sustainability of material use, particularly for resources like rare earth metals, which are essential for wind turbines and batteries. This metric encourages the adoption of alternative materials or more efficient resource use to prevent depletion and ensure the long-term sustainability of renewable energy technologies and supply chains.

Table 3: Resource Use and Sustainability KPIs

Indicator	Description	Unit	Formula	Relevance	Pros	Cons
Water Footprint	The total volume of water consumed during the energy system's lifecycle, from construction to operation and decommissioning.	Cubic meters (m ³)	Water Footprint = Water Used during Construction + Operation + Decommissioning	Important for evaluating the water use efficiency of renewable projects, especially in water-scarce regions.	Useful for understanding water use in water-scarce regions; Important for sustainability assessments in resource-limited areas	Ignores other environmental impacts; Can be complex to calculate accurately for large-scale systems; Focuses only on water consumption
Land Use Impact	The amount of land area required for the energy system's infrastructure and operations.	Hectares (ha)	Land Use Impact = Total Land Area Occupied / Total Energy Produced	Relevant for understanding the ecological footprint and habitat disruption, especially for land-intensive renewables like solar farms.	Measures ecological footprint in terms of land area; Critical for large-scale solar and wind projects; Highlights habitat disruption	Ignores energy production efficiency; Does not account for multiple land-use benefits; Can disadvantage projects with large land footprints
Embodied Energy in Materials	Refers to the total energy required to produce and deliver materials used in constructing renewable energy systems.	Megajoules (MJ)	Embodied Energy = Σ (Energy for Material Extraction + Processing + Transportation)	This metric helps assess the hidden energy costs embedded in renewable projects, aiding in lifecycle analysis.	Highlights hidden energy costs in material production and transportation; Important for lifecycle sustainability assessments	Requires detailed supply chain data; Ignores operational energy use and other environmental impacts

<p>Resource Depletion Index (RDI)</p>	<p>Measures the depletion of non-renewable and critical materials used in the construction and operation of renewable energy systems.</p>	<p>Index (unitless)</p>	<p>$RDI = \Sigma (\text{Quantity of Non-Renewable Materials Used} / \text{Global Reserves})$</p>	<p>RDI is critical for assessing the sustainability of material use, particularly rare or non-renewable resources.</p>	<p>Highlights reliance on non-renewable resources; Important for long-term material sustainability</p>	<p>Difficult to quantify accurately for complex systems; Does not account for recycling or material substitution potential</p>
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Ecosystem and Biodiversity KPIs

Biodiversity impact quantifies the effects of renewable energy projects on local ecosystems, including habitat disruption, species displacement, and loss of biodiversity (Karlsson et al., 2022). This indicator is vital for ensuring that renewable energy projects do not harm the local environment or endangered species and can demonstrate an improvement against non-renewable alternatives. Impacts are measured using biodiversity loss indices that assess the extent of species affected and the severity of the disruption. By tracking this indicator, project developers can implement mitigation strategies, such as habitat restoration or species relocation, to minimize ecological damage and contribute to the sustainability of the energy transition (Narain et al., 2022).

Ecosystem services impact assesses the effect of renewable energy projects on critical ecosystem functions such as water regulation, carbon sequestration, pollination, and soil formation (Briones-Hidrovo et al., 2020). Measured as an index, this indicator helps stakeholders understand how a project affects ecosystem services that support human and environmental well-being. By considering these impacts, project developers can design strategies to minimize harm and maximize co-benefits, such as habitat creation or improved biodiversity. This holistic approach ensures that renewable energy projects contribute to sustainable development goals without undermining the ecosystems that communities and industries depend on.

Visual impact assesses the aesthetic effect of renewable energy projects on the surrounding landscape (Spielhofer et al., 2021). This metric is particularly relevant for wind farms and large solar installations, which can significantly alter the visual environment. A high visual impact can lead to public opposition, particularly in areas of natural beauty or close to residential zones. Minimizing visual intrusion through careful site selection, design, and stakeholder engagement can help improve the acceptance of renewable energy projects. The visual impact assessment ensures that projects are developed in harmony with the environment and local communities (Szumilas-Kowalczyk et al., 2020).

The Cumulative Ecological Impact (CEI) measures the total long-term effect of renewable energy projects on ecosystems (Rudman et al., 2017). This metric accounts for both immediate and lasting environmental disturbances, such as habitat fragmentation, biodiversity loss, and ecosystem disruption. By aggregating impacts over time, CEI provides a comprehensive assessment of how renewable energy systems affect natural ecosystems beyond the construction and operational phases. It helps stakeholders identify cumulative impacts from multiple projects in the same area, ensuring that the aggregated ecological footprint is considered in decision-making, allowing for better mitigation and environmental restoration strategies.

Table 4: Ecosystem and Biodiversity KPIs

Indicator	Description	Unit	Formula	Relevance	Pros	Cons
Biodiversity Impact	Measures the negative effects of the energy system on local biodiversity, including habitat disruption and species loss.	Biodiversity Loss Index (unitless)	Biodiversity Impact = Σ (Species Affected * Impact Factor)	Critical for ensuring that renewable projects are ecologically sustainable and do not harm local ecosystems.	Critical for assessing the ecological sustainability of projects; Highlights potential harm to ecosystems and endangered species	Can be difficult to quantify biodiversity losses; Requires extensive environmental impact assessments; Mitigation measures may be costly
Ecosystem Services Impact	The effect of renewable energy systems on local ecosystem services, such as water regulation, carbon sequestration, and pollination.	Index (unitless)	Ecosystem Services Impact = Σ (Impact on Service Type * Impact Severity)	Critical for assessing the broader ecological effects of renewable energy projects on ecosystems beyond direct biodiversity impacts.	Measures broader ecosystem benefits like water regulation, carbon sequestration; Important for long-term sustainability assessments	Difficult to quantify and monetize; Requires a holistic approach to environmental analysis; Can be costly to mitigate losses

<p>Visual Impact</p>	<p>Assesses the effect of the renewable energy system on the visual landscape, often a concern for wind farms or solar arrays.</p>	<p>Visual Impact Score (unitless)</p>	<p>Visual Impact = (Degree of Visual Intrusion * Area Affected)</p>	<p>Relevant for public acceptance and the aesthetic integration of renewable projects into landscapes.</p>	<p>Highlights social and environmental concerns for nearby communities; Important for public acceptance of renewable projects</p>	<p>Highly subjective and location-dependent; Difficult to mitigate completely, especially in natural landscapes</p>
<p>Cumulative Ecological Impact (CEI)</p>	<p>Measures the total cumulative effect of renewable energy projects on ecosystems over time.</p>	<p>Index (unitless)</p>	<p>$CEI = \sum (\text{Impact per System Component} * \text{Duration of Impact})$</p>	<p>CEI is crucial for understanding the long-term and aggregated effects of multiple renewable energy projects on ecosystems.</p>	<p>Provides a comprehensive view of long-term and aggregated ecological impacts; Important for assessing the overall footprint of projects</p>	<p>Can be complex to calculate for large or multiple projects; Requires long-term monitoring and data collection</p>

Waste Management and End-of-Life KPIs

The end-of-life recycling rate refers to the percentage of materials that can be recycled when a renewable energy system is decommissioned (Nassar et al., 2016). This indicator is crucial for assessing the circular economy potential of renewable energy technologies. A higher recycling rate reduces waste and lowers the environmental impact associated with disposing of system components like solar panels, wind turbine blades and towers, and batteries (Jones & Li, 2023). By improving recycling practices, renewable energy projects can minimize their overall ecological footprint, reduce demand for raw materials, and contribute to a more sustainable, resource-efficient energy sector in the long term.

Waste generation tracks the total amount of waste produced during the construction, operation, and decommissioning of renewable energy systems. Measured in tons, this indicator is important for understanding the environmental impact of material use, particularly in resource-intensive projects like offshore wind farms or solar panel installations. Minimizing waste generation through better design, material efficiency, and recycling can significantly reduce the environmental footprint of renewable energy projects. By managing waste effectively, developers can ensure compliance with environmental regulations and contribute to the sustainability of the energy industry.

The Material Circularity Index (MCI) measures the degree to which materials used in renewable energy systems are sourced from recycled content and are recyclable at the end of the system's life (Abokersh et al., 2021). A higher MCI indicates better alignment with circular economy principles, minimizing resource extraction and waste generation. This metric is critical for renewable energy projects that rely on high volumes of materials, such as solar panels or wind turbines. By promoting the use of recycled materials and improving recyclability, MCI helps reduce the environmental footprint and supports a sustainable lifecycle approach to renewable energy development (Rambau et al., 2024).

Table 5: Waste Management and End-of-life KPIs

Indicator	Description	Unit	Formula	Relevance	Pros	Cons
End-of-Life Recycling Rate	The percentage of materials that can be recycled after the renewable energy system reaches the end of its life.	Percentage (%)	End-of-Life Recycling Rate = (Recycled Materials / Total System Materials) * 100	Important for determining the circular economy potential of renewable energy systems, reducing the environmental impact of waste.	Critical for promoting circular economy principles; Reduces waste and environmental impact at the end of system life	Can be difficult to implement in practice, particularly for complex systems like wind turbines; Recycling processes can be costly
Waste Generation	The total amount of waste produced during the energy system's construction, operation, and decommissioning phases.	Tons of waste (t)	Waste Generation = Σ (Waste during Construction + Operation + Decommissioning)	Relevant for evaluating the environmental impact of material use and disposal, particularly in construction-intensive renewable energy projects.	Highlights the environmental impact of material use; Important for minimizing resource use and promoting waste reduction	Focuses only on material waste, ignoring energy or water impacts; Waste disposal processes may vary by region
Material Circularity Index (MCI)	Assesses the degree to which materials used in renewable energy systems are sourced from recycled content and are recyclable at end-of-life.	Percentage (%)	MCI = (Recycled Material / Total Material Input) * 100	Critical for promoting the circular economy and reducing waste in renewable energy supply chains.	Encourages the use of recycled materials and promotes recyclability; Important for advancing the circular economy in energy systems	Recycling processes may not always be available; Difficult to implement in complex systems like wind turbines or solar panels

Energy Efficiency and Investment Return KPIs

Renewable Energy Return on Investment (EROI) measures the ratio of energy output to the energy input required to build, operate, and decommission a renewable energy system (Trainer, 2018). It is a critical metric for evaluating the energy efficiency of renewable technologies. A higher EROI means that the system generates significantly more energy over its lifetime than the energy invested in creating and maintaining it. This indicator is essential for comparing the sustainability of different renewable technologies. Systems with a higher EROI contribute more effectively to reducing the global reliance on fossil fuels and advancing toward energy independence (Raugei, 2019b).

The Ecological Footprint per kWh assesses the total ecological burden (land, water, and material use) associated with generating one kilowatt-hour of electricity (Al-mulali et al., 2016). This metric helps compare the resource efficiency of different renewable energy technologies. By accounting for the land area, water consumption, and material inputs needed for energy production, EF/kWh highlights trade-offs between energy generation and environmental conservation (Gao et al., 2021). Renewable energy systems with lower ecological footprints are more sustainable, as they use fewer natural resources to generate power, reducing the overall impact on ecosystems and promoting environmental balance alongside energy development.

The Environmental Payback Period (EPP) calculates the time it takes for a renewable energy system to offset its own environmental impacts (e.g., carbon emissions, water use, resource depletion) through clean energy generation (Amini Toosi et al., 2022). A shorter EPP indicates that the project becomes environmentally net-positive more quickly. This metric is essential for assessing the long-term sustainability of renewable energy projects, ensuring that the environmental costs incurred during construction and deployment are outweighed by the benefits of clean energy production. EPP is especially important for justifying the development of large-scale renewable systems.

Net Environmental Benefit measures the total positive environmental impact of a renewable energy project after accounting for all environmental costs (e.g., emissions, resource use, waste generation) (Mahian et al., 2021). This metric provides a comprehensive view of whether a renewable energy project creates more environmental benefits (e.g., emissions reductions, clean energy production) than harms. A positive net environmental benefit signifies that the project contributes to overall sustainability and environmental health. This KPI helps decision-makers balance trade-offs between project benefits and costs, ensuring that renewable energy development supports broader environmental and sustainability goals.

Table 6: Energy Efficiency and Investment Return KPIs

Indicator	Description	Unit	Formula	Relevance	Pros	Cons
Renewable Energy Return on Investment (EROI)	Measures the energy output compared to the energy input over the system's lifetime.	Ratio	$EROI = \text{Total Energy Output} / \text{Total Energy Input}$	Essential for assessing the energy efficiency and overall sustainability of renewable energy technologies.	Measures energy efficiency, ensuring more energy is produced than consumed; Important for long-term energy sustainability assessments	Does not account for other environmental factors like land use or emissions; Can vary greatly across technologies and locations
Ecological Footprint per kWh (EF/kWh)	Assesses the total ecological footprint (land, water, and resource use) required to generate one kilowatt-hour of electricity.	Global hectares per kWh (gha/kWh)	$\text{Ecological Footprint per kWh} = \Sigma (\text{Land, Water, and Resource Use}) / \text{Total Energy Produced}$	Helps compare the land and resource efficiency of different renewable energy technologies.	Measures resource efficiency by linking environmental impact to energy production; Useful for comparing different energy technologies	Ignores broader environmental and social factors; Does not account for intermittency or demand matching

<p>Environmental Payback Period (EPP)</p>	<p>The time it takes for a renewable energy system to offset its own environmental impacts (e.g., carbon emissions, water use) through clean energy generation.</p>	<p>Time (years)</p>	<p>$EPP = \frac{\text{Total Environmental Impact}}{\text{Annual Environmental Savings}}$</p>	<p>EPP is crucial for understanding how quickly renewable energy projects become environmentally net-positive.</p>	<p>Measures how long it takes for a system to offset its own environmental impacts; Useful for lifecycle sustainability assessments</p>	<p>Requires accurate environmental impact data; Can vary greatly across different technologies and locations</p>
<p>Net Environmental Benefit</p>	<p>The total net positive impact of the renewable energy system after subtracting all environmental costs (e.g., emissions, resource use, waste) from the environmental benefits of clean energy production.</p>	<p>Environmental Benefit Index (unitless)</p>	<p>$\text{Net Environmental Benefit} = \text{Environmental Benefits} - \text{Environmental Costs}$</p>	<p>Provides a holistic view of whether renewable energy projects generate net-positive environmental outcomes.</p>	<p>Provides a holistic view of the overall environmental gains after accounting for negative impacts; Important for assessing net sustainability</p>	<p>Difficult to quantify comprehensively; Requires data on all environmental impacts and benefits over the project lifecycle</p>

Climate Resilience and Global Impact KPIs

Climate resilience evaluates the capacity of a renewable energy system to withstand and adapt to changing climate conditions, such as extreme weather events, temperature shifts, or sea-level rise (Nik et al., 2021). This metric is crucial for ensuring long-term operational stability in a world facing increasing climate variability. Renewable energy systems that are climate-resilient can maintain their performance and reliability despite environmental stressors (Anderson & Van Bossuyt, 2024). Developers must design systems with adaptive capacity to minimize risks from climate-related disruptions, ensuring continuous energy generation and contributing to the resilience of the energy infrastructure.

Global Warming Potential (GWP) quantifies the total contribution of a renewable energy system to climate change by measuring the combined impact of all greenhouse gases (GHGs) emitted over its lifecycle (Cho et al., 2023). GWP considers emissions from CO₂, methane, and other GHGs, expressed in terms of CO₂ equivalents (CO₂e). This metric is vital for comparing the climate impact of different renewable energy systems. By measuring GWP, stakeholders can identify opportunities to reduce emissions, prioritize low-impact technologies, and support renewable energy solutions that offer the greatest benefits in combating global climate change (Khan et al., 2024).

Table 7: Climate Resilience and Global Impact KPIs

Indicator	Description	Unit	Formula	Relevance	Pros	Cons
Climate Resilience	Evaluates the ability of the energy system to withstand and adapt to changing climate conditions, such as extreme weather events.	Resilience Score (unitless)	Climate Resilience = Σ (Adaptation Measures * Effectiveness)	Important for future-proofing renewable energy projects and ensuring long-term operational stability under changing climate conditions.	Critical for ensuring long-term system stability under climate change; Helps identify and mitigate climate-related risks	Difficult to quantify climate resilience benefits; Requires consideration of a range of uncertain future scenarios
Global Warming Potential (GWP)	Measures the total contribution of a renewable energy system to global warming over its lifecycle, considering all greenhouse gases.	Metric tons CO ₂ e	GWP = Σ (Emissions of all GHGs * Global Warming Potentials)	GWP helps quantify the total climate impact of a renewable energy system, making it a critical component of lifecycle assessments.	Quantifies the overall climate impact of all greenhouse gases emitted; Useful for assessing long-term climate change mitigation	Requires detailed emissions data; Ignores other environmental impacts like biodiversity loss or water use

3.2. Socio-economic KPIs

This part of the deliverable aims to help project partners to identify KPIs relevant for the social and societal aspects of the implementation of FOW infrastructure. This subsection gives an overview of relevant societal impact KPIs identified through the literature review, and in particular indicators measuring contribution of projects to community and cultural synergy. The work done highlighted some specific issues to consider:

- It is necessary to understand the key societal impacts of renewable energy systems;
- It is necessary to develop social KPIs that ensure community and cultural synergy at local level;
- The Societal Readiness Level (SRL) framework can be relevant to some extent, but it is still not properly developed in general terms and not validated for renewable energy projects.

Compared to other categories of indicators, the literature analysed highlights a lower degree of consensus among practitioners on the appropriate indicators for societal impacts. This can be related to them being sensitive to a specific context (e.g. location and characteristics of projects); on their dependence on self-reported user variables; on the extent to which they are affected by the definition of boundaries for measuring impacts (e.g. the definition of what is meant by “local”).

To build this section, a targeted review of the literature has been performed, starting from recent and comprehensive “reviews of reviews” (e.g. Colla et.al. 2020 and Afshari et.al. 2022). The review led to the identification of a longlist of indicators. This has been further narrowed down based on relevance of each KPI to the topic of focus (renewable energy projects), and measurability. Note that a tighter specification of indicators would be required when utilising these for specific assessments and decision-making questions (e.g. whether a comparison of projects extends to different types of renewable energy, or it is limited to wind energy). Additional selection criteria should be applied when selecting and specifying indicators for applied use within a specific project (e.g. see indicators outlined by Gebara et al. 2024).

Metrics for assessing the social impacts of projects can be helpful to understand and influence the level of social acceptance in relation to a specific project. As a way of background, social acceptance refers to the degree to which individuals, communities, and stakeholders support or oppose a research and innovation project, and in this specific case, a renewable energy projects.

In the context of floating offshore wind energy, this involves attitudes toward the technology, its benefits, and its potential impacts on local communities, economies, and environments. While there is high acceptance of renewable energy projects in Europe, this varies widely based on technology. A survey for the European Climate Foundation concluded that 86% of people would support new renewable energy projects near where they live, but this falls to only 62% for wind energy projects. There are multiple reasons for this lower acceptance, ranging from:

- aesthetics and impact on the landscape;
- the impact on wildlife;
- the belief that noise or visual flicker will negatively affect their comfort;
- the belief that wind farms change land-use from leisure or agricultural uses;

- cost effectiveness considerations compared to other technologies.

Others simply do not consider wind turbines to be a cost-effective solution, compared to other energy technologies. To build social acceptance of wind technologies, policymakers have developed various solutions for bringing people on board.

All infrastructure projects, regardless of their energy source, affect the local communities where they are sited. Without sufficient engagement and buy-in from local communities, power projects can face delays, cost overruns, and cancellation if communities do not perceive tangible benefits from the power infrastructure investment.

On this topic for example, as support to the implementation phase, USAID released a guide to help policymakers address the social impact of auctions¹ using auction design options such as conditions for participation, bid award criteria, and local value creation (USAID, 2022).

For analysing and measuring societal impact, some key determinants and dimensions should be taken into consideration and used to define specific KPIs – which in turn could then be used for further analysis such as a Social Life Cycle Assessment (SLCA) analysis or Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) assessment. Some key dimensions have been found in the literature as significant, and relevant to the assessment of renewable energy projects:

1. Impacts on local economy including job creation;
2. Working conditions;
3. Local workforce upskilling and reskilling;
4. Impacts on landscape and social acceptance.

We will go through these dimensions by highlighting some specific issues arising from the literature and providing suggested indicators for each of these areas.

Impacts on local economy including job creation

This category includes a set of indicators that is key for energy sector decision-makers to understand how their projects can affect local communities and economies. The proposed shortlist of indicators within this category is described in this sub-section and synthesised in the table below. The table includes also the main reference where the indicator has been sourced from, alongside additional supporting evidence, although most of these indicators are widely cited in the literature.

The **local content ratio** metric is particularly relevant to industries like construction or energy. It measures the proportion of total costs or activities that are sourced locally, including labour, services, and materials.

This indicator is used by international organisations such as ILO and the World Bank as part of their assessment of sustainable development. For example, this is included in the World Bank report: Local Content Policies in the Extractive Sector: Lessons from the World Bank's Experience which also discusses the broader social and economic implications of promoting local employment and resources.

The indicator is also used by specific industries as part of their Corporate Social Responsibility reporting.

¹ USAID, 2022: <https://www.usaid.gov/energy/auctions/social-impacts>

This ratio might combine local labour, materials, and other services, providing a broader picture of local economic impact. It can incorporate the following sub-components:

- **Local Employment Impact (LEI):** the LEI is often used in development projects to measure the extent to which a project contributes to local job creation. It can involve both direct and indirect jobs created by the project.
- **Labour Sourcing Ratio:** in some cases, projects or companies track the local labour sourcing ratio specifically to assess the sustainability of their workforce. This metric often includes the percentage of labour sourced from a specific geographic area or community, and it's particularly relevant for large, capital-intensive projects (e.g., infrastructure or mining).

The indicator of **local changes in tourism-related businesses**, widely used and cited for example by Afshari et al (2022), is used as a social sustainability indicator in the energy sector to measure the potential impact of energy projects on surrounding tourism-related businesses. It can be particularly relevant for offshore wind projects as those projects are likely to interact with other uses of marine space including for recreational purposes.

The indicator for **new positions supported or created** is also used as a social sustainability indicator in the energy sector. It falls under the category of occupational indicators and focuses on aspects related to the work environment, evaluating new employment opportunities. Job creation can be particularly relevant for the development of local communities, contributing to their economic and social growth and reducing unemployment. For this purpose, it is important to relate this indicator to the other metrics mentioned above, measuring local employment impacts.

Table 8: Impact on local economy and job creation

Indicator	Description	Unit	Formula	Data Source	Relevance	Pros	Cons
Local content Ratio	Proportion of total costs or activities that are sourced locally, including labour, services, and materials	Ratio	Local Content Ratio = Value of Local Inputs / Total Value of Inputs	Data from local companies and local statistics.	This indicator is relevant for the extent to which such a kind of infrastructure can impact local value chains in terms of creation of opportunities for local industries. This is mostly used in extractive industries but can be adapted	Can inform research on local economic impacts of wind turbines	The specific definition of 'local inputs' and the methodology for calculating their value can differ based on national policies and the particular goals of local content initiatives; lack of reliable data
Share of income to local companies	Percentage of income from new projects that goes to local companies	Ratio	Registered income to local companies/total registered income.	Revenue data from companies involved in project	The indicator specifies the part of income generated by implementation of new FOW parks on total of registered income for the value chain	Can inform to T5.4 research on local economic impacts of wind turbines	Need careful definition of "local", might be difficult to measure do to lack of reliable data
Share of labour sourced locally	Percentage of jobs associated to project that are taken up by residents	Ratio	Number of resident workers hired/Total number of hired workers	Occupational data from companies involved in the project	The indicator specifies how much the project can benefit local value	Can inform to T5.4 research on local economic impacts of wind turbines	Need careful definition of "local", might be difficult to measure do to

					chains in terms of job creation for residents		lack of reliable data
New positions supports / created	New working positions created by project activities	Number of jobs	Total number of jobs created	Jobs data from companies (Colla et. al. 2020)	The indicator states the number of jobs created in general by the installation of FOW infrastructure at local level not only for residents	Found in large body of literature, important to assess impacts on local economy	Might have issues around data availability
Local changes in tourism related business	Measuring any increase or decrease of tourism following implementation, in the area where project is located	% change	Increment or decrement in number of tourists after the installation (data should be somehow standardized by avoiding interferences from other factors)	Survey data from local businesses Data from tourism offices Local/national statistics on tourism (Afshari et. al. 2022)	The indicator reflects and combines the societal impact indicators in terms of how much the local tourism is affected by the installation of a FOW parks.	Can inform research on local economic impacts of wind turbines	Need careful definition of "local", need sufficient resource to carry out survey, meaningful effects might go beyond project timelines

Working conditions

The measurement of metrics in this area allows a more rounded assessment of the quality of jobs supported or created by energy projects, in addition to the aspects related to the training of local workforce that will be discussed in the next paragraph.

The **average salary** indicator is used as a measure of social sustainability within the scope of occupational indicators, as part of assessing fairness and working conditions within an organization or sector. The average salary indicator is often used to evaluate whether employees receive fair and just compensation for their work. The average salary can serve as an indicator to assess the social impact of a company or a project, particularly on local communities. Generally, calculation methods may include:

- Arithmetic Mean: the sum of all employees' salaries divided by the total number of employees;
- Average by Category: calculating the average salaries for specific employee categories (e.g., by level, role, seniority);
- Comparison with Minimum Wage: the ratio between the average salary and the local minimum wage, to assess whether employees receive a decent wage.
- Salary Ratio: comparison between the average salary of managers and that of employees, to highlight potential imbalances.

The **total accident rate** indicator is a key metric for assessing occupational health and safety (HSE), measuring the frequency of workplace injuries over a specific period. This indicator is essential for evaluating the effectiveness of company safety policies and for monitoring the risks workers are exposed to. A change in this indicator following the introduction of a new technology can assess whether this can be associated to a higher level of safety for workers. This indicator alone has some limitations hence it should be assessed alongside other indicators on working conditions.

The indicator on **labour wellbeing** appears for example in Ahmad and Wong (2019). This indicator can be measured through self-reported measures from employee survey data. It is an important integration to the accident rate indicator which focuses on physical health, as it also covers emotional wellbeing and mental health dimensions.

Other indicators related to the quality of jobs related to a specific project include the positive impact of reduced installation noise on wellbeing, and an index of workforce diversity (that can be seen as a proxy of the degree of inclusiveness of the workplace).

Table 9: Working conditions

Indicator	Description	Unit	Formula	Data Source	Relevance	Pros	Cons
Average salary	Salary offered in new positions compared to local average	Ratio	Salary offered by companies in FOW value chain/average salaries in local industries	Salary data from companies; national and local statistics (Afshari et al. 2022)	This indicator can reflect the higher or lower attractiveness of the sector respect to local industries in terms of job salaries	Found in large body of literature, important to measure impacts on human capital and quality of working conditions	Need careful definition of local; might have issues around data availability
Change in total accident rate	Measures if accident rate (e.g. related to installation & O&M) is higher or lower after introduction of technology	Ratio	accidents/ 100 site visits/ operations	Data from companies on accident on the job (Pfaffel et al 2019)	The indicator can be used to define the extent to which FOW installation is safer than other type of renewable energy	Can help assess whether a new technology is associated to a higher level of safety for workers.	It ignores the severity of injuries; there are standardisation challenges across companies; lacks insight on causes.
Positive impact of reduced installation noise	Self-reported measure of benefits by employees	Likert scale	Perceived reduction of noise and reported benefits on wellbeing	User survey (Carrera & Mack 2010)	This indicator is related to general wellbeing of workers and this aspect will be included in the analysis of	Integrates technical KPI on noise reduction	Subjectivity of self-reported measures

					the installation process within the project		
Labour reported wellbeing	Self-reported measures by employees – perceived wellbeing	Likert scale	Number of respondents to surveys that answer positively or negatively to specific items through likert scales	Employee survey (Ahmad and Wong 2019; Afshari et al 2022)	This indicator can offer an understanding on how workers in the FOW value chain perceive wellbeing in relation to different variables that can affect their job such as benefits, working conditions, attractiveness of the installation site, local services (such as hospitals, mobility, social, etc...)	Integrates aspects of job satisfaction that are relevant for the socio-economic wellbeing	Need robust survey design; subjective measure from small sample
Workforce diversity	Change in workforce gender balance and ethnicity	Ratio	% share of female/ male; % share of	Company socio-	The indicator is relevant to understand	Can help assess whether a	Might have issue of data availability; might not provide

<p>(gender, ethnicity)</p>	<p>representation (before and after project or new technology implementation)</p>		<p>ethnic minorities</p>	<p>economic statistics (Ahmad et al 2019)</p>	<p>potential differences in terms of presence of male and female in the industry, trade-offs in work time and family time, presence of minorities, need of different languages, need to communicate in a proper way</p>	<p>specific project or new technology is associated to a better workforce diversity</p>	<p>any meaningful results</p>
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Local workforce upskilling and reskilling

This category of indicators contains all the relevant aspects related to the local workforce when considering the wider impact that a new FOW infrastructure can have on the local socio-economic system.

The indicator measuring **change in skill level of new positions** forms part of occupational indicators. It is crucial for evaluating the social sustainability of energy projects, as it helps measure not only how many jobs are created but also the quality of these jobs and their impact on the professional and personal growth of workers, evaluating how these new roles contribute to the development of workforce skills. The change in skill level is often linked to continuous training and professional retraining programs offered by employers, which are essential to ensure employees can adapt to new technologies and the ever-changing needs of the energy sector. Increasing the skill level of the workforce is associated with a positive impact on the local community, making it more competitive and resilient to economic challenges, as communities with a skilled workforce are more attractive for future investments and hence it can foster sustainable economic growth.

Employee training is connected to and can directly influence change in skills level, and hence it is related to human capital increase.

The measurement of this indicator must consider the specificity of the training. For example, green employee training focuses on providing specific skills and knowledge related to environmental sustainability, such as energy efficiency, waste reduction, the use of renewable energy, and other environmentally friendly practices.

Training can be quantitative (e.g., number of training hours, number of employees trained) or qualitative (e.g., evaluation of training effectiveness, participant feedback). Qualitative indicators are more complex and may build on the evaluation of training effectiveness (feedback questionnaires, learning tests, field observations); changes in employee behaviour (reduction of energy consumption, improved waste management, adoption of safer work practices); and participant feedback.

Table 10: Local workforce upskilling and reskilling

Indicator	Description	Proposed unit	Formula	Data Source	Relevance	Pros	Cons
Change in skill level of new positions	Measures if changes in job structure result in higher grades within the same company/ sector	Grade distribution, by sector	Data on employee grades from companies, before and after	Afshari et. al. 2022	This indicator is relevant for the definition of the baseline for the workforce to be hired for FOW implementation	Found in large body of literature, important to measure impacts on human capital and quality of working conditions	Might have issues around data availability
Employee training	Training received by employees, upskilling, green economy-related skills	N trainings	Training data from companies	Afshari et. al. 2022	This is relevant for having skilled workforce at local level and it has a correlation with salaries and wellbeing	Found in large body of literature, relevant for assessing benefits renewable energy projects	Need careful definition of “green” if using; might have issues around data availability

Impact on landscape and social acceptance

Last section addresses the assessment of impacts on landscape, related environmental concerns, and overall social acceptability of a specific renewable energy technology.

Wind farm installations can cause opposition due to aesthetic degradation, noise, and the risk of bird collisions (Buchmayr et al 2022). Aesthetic impact and environmental concerns metrics are both associated to the impacts of energy projects on landscape, and they often appear to affect social acceptance. **Aesthetic impact** can be assessed through self-reported measures by community members; as such it provides a subjective measure which can be affected by measurement bias. **Environmental concerns** are also an important element that can determine social acceptance, as reported for example by Hubner et. al. (2023). Information about reduced environmental impacts can be measured through environmental indicators and disseminated to reduce such concerns.

Social acceptance is a critical indicator in assessing sustainability, particularly in the energy sector, reflecting public perceptions and reactions to projects and technologies.

This is crucial because public opinion can significantly influence the success or failure of an initiative (Carrera and Mack 2010). It reflects stakeholder concerns and community interests, which are essential for effective and sustainable management plans (Marques et al 2013), and thus it is a way to measure the level of support or opposition from the public to a specific technology or project.

Social acceptance can be measured in various ways for instance: surveys and questionnaires; expert Interviews; group Delphi Method⁴; workshops and public meetings; Participatory Development for Stakeholder Engagement (PDSE). The effective measurement of social acceptance involves a multifaceted approach that combines different methods of data collection and actively engages stakeholders.

Social acceptance is inherently subjective and can vary greatly across different social and cultural contexts and hence it can be difficult to quantify, making it hard to compare different projects or technologies directly. It is affected by emotional influence and data availability.

We included in this section two indicators which could be relevant for what regards social and environmental concerns: **reported decrease in conflicts with other sea users** and **reduced fishing exclusion zones**. Although these indicators are purely qualitative, it should be useful to consider them to match environmental and social concerns when working with local stakeholder in the blue economy and in particular fisheries to design socially acceptable strategies to implement FOW parks.

Table 11: Impact on landscape and social acceptance

Indicator	Description	Proposed unit	Formula	Data Source	Relevance	Pros	Cons
Impact on landscape: aesthetic impact	Self-reported measure by community members	Quantitative value to qualitative attributes (e.g. Likert scale)	Survey data to local population	Carrera & Mack 2010	This is a relevant issue depending on the place of installation	Useful to understand results on social acceptance	Subjective measure from small sample
Impact on landscape: environmental concerns	Self-reported measure by community members	Quantitative value to qualitative attributes (e.g. Likert scale)	Survey data to local population	Hubner et al 2023	This is relevant for the coexistence of different marine users	Useful to understand results on social acceptance	Subjective measure from small sample
Social acceptance	Acceptability of project/ technology by local community	Qualitative index	Survey data to local population	Colla et. al. 2020, widely researched question	The relevance of this indicator is largely depending on the data sources and the availability of stakeholders in participating to workshops and focus groups	Key for implementation	Measurability challenges; need careful definition/ survey design
Reported decrease in conflict with other sea users	Self-reported measure by stakeholders in different sea user groups	Likert scale 1-5	Number of respondents to surveys that answer positively or negatively to specific items	Survey data from other selected sea users (fisheries, tourism, sports)	This indicator should reflect the opportunity to engage relevant stakeholders from sea user groups before	Indicator would be demonstrating that expected impacts identified at proposal stage take place	Need sufficient resource to carry out survey, meaningful effects might go beyond project timelines

			through likert scales	Grant Agreement	taking decisions on the installation of a FOW plant to reduce conflicts		
Reduced fishing exclusion zones	Decrease in the marine space that is classified as fishing exclusion zone	Km2	Official data on fishing exclusion zones before /after implementation (km2 of protected marine space)	National and regional datasets	This indicator is relevant to define the expected consequence of reduced environmental impacts and more efficient use of marine space	Indicator would be demonstrating that expected impacts identified at proposal stage take place	Meaningful effects might go beyond project timelines

Conclusions

This deliverable reports findings of Task 5.1, and focuses on a comprehensive review of sustainability-related Key Performance Indicators for Floating Offshore Wind (FOW) technologies, with a particular emphasis on environmental and socio-economic dimensions. It expands upon the technical and financial KPI framework introduced in D1.2 and offers a structured basis for integrated sustainability assessments across the TAILWIND project.

Through a combination of systematic literature review, alignment with international standards (e.g., ILO, USAID), and project-specific context, the report has identified a robust set of 46 environmental and 18 socio-economic KPIs. These have been categorized into key thematic areas including emissions and pollution, resource use, biodiversity impacts, waste and end-of-life considerations, energy efficiency, climate resilience, local economic effects, working conditions, skills development, and social acceptance. Each indicator is detailed in terms of calculation methodology, data sources, and relevance to the sustainability of FOW systems.

Importantly, this work provides the foundation for tailoring sustainability metrics to technology-specific and site-specific contexts, enabling a more nuanced evaluation of innovations within TAILWIND. The multi-dimensional nature of the KPI set is aligned with evolving procurement and regulatory practices that increasingly move beyond LCOE-centric evaluation frameworks towards integrated environmental and social value assessments.

The framework developed herein will directly inform subsequent activities in WP3 (Evaluation of sustainable anchor concepts) and WP5 (Integrated impact assessment and benchmarking), particularly Task 5.4, where these KPIs will be operationalized in site-specific assessments and decision-support tools. Future work will involve:

- Engagement with stakeholders and project partners to validate the relevance and practicality of the KPI shortlist, especially in the context of different deployment environments and marine spatial planning constraints.
- The indicators will be embedded into sustainability assessment models, including social life cycle assessments (S-LCA) and multicriteria decision analysis (MCDA) frameworks, to enable comparative evaluations of technology configurations and design options.
- Efforts will be made to harmonize KPI definitions and impact metrics with other related EU-funded initiatives to support interoperability and promote sector-wide benchmarking practices.
- The development of composite sustainability indices and scenario-based simulation tools will facilitate quantitative trade-off analyses and aggregation of multidimensional impacts into unified performance metrics, aligning with emerging requirements for green public procurement and sustainability-linked auctions.
- Continuous alignment with European Green Deal targets and evolving sustainability taxonomies (e.g., EU Taxonomy Regulation) will ensure that the

KPI framework remains relevant and supportive of future regulatory and investment frameworks.

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